

METALLIC COMPLEXES OF TARTARIC AND CITRIC ACIDS.
PART I. COPPER-TARTARIC ACID

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From conductometric and absorption measurements it has been shown that in dilute solution cupric ion forms with tartaric acid a complex containing the metal and tartrate in the proportion of 1:1. By utilising Job's method of continued variation the instability constant of the complex has been calculated and found to be 1.21×10^{-2} .

It is well known that the presence of tartaric acid or alkali tartrates interferes with the quantitative estimation of copper. The cause is attributed to the formation of a complex the exact nature of which is not definitely known, in spite of the considerable work which has been done. The object of the present investigation is to study the above reaction thoroughly from different physico-chemical standpoints. Conductometric and absorption measurements have been made to ascertain the course of the reaction, and by utilising Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 180, 926) the nature of the complex and the extent of its dissociation have been calculated.

Earlier work is confined to the isolation of compounds by fractional precipitation with alcohol from solution of copper tartrate dissolved in varying quantities of alkali (Masson and Steele, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1839, 76, 725; Pickering, *ibid.*, 1910, 97, 1837; 1911, 99, 169, 1347; 1912, 101, 174; Packer and Warck, *ibid.*, 1921, 119, 1348; Warck, *ibid.*, 1923, 123, 1815, 1826; 1927, 1753). They isolated several compounds containing varying proportions of copper, tartrate and alkali metals. Dumansky and Chalisew (*Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 42, 121) have contended that they are not definite compounds but merely colloidal suspensions of cupric hydroxide in neutral or alkaline tartrate. From the physico-chemical standpoint the reaction was first studied by Jelinek and Gordon (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 112, 207). From the e. m. f. measurements of an electrode of the metal in a tartrate solution of small hydrogen-ion concentration containing a small amount of the metal salt they concluded that in acid solution copper and tartrate ions reacted to form a complex in the proportion of 1:1.

Shinichiro and Hakomori (*Sci. Rep. Tōhōku Imp. Univ.*, 1927, 16, 841) supported this view from the study of the reaction of the metal in presence of tartaric acid by means of absorption spectrum, electrical conductivity, optical rotation, etc. in acid, neutral and ammoniacal medium. Recently Bobtelsky and Jordan (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 1824) have studied the reaction by means of electrical conductivity and absorption and p_H measurements in dilute aqueous and 50% alcoholic solutions and have expressed the view that bivalent cations form

no complex with free acid but complexes are formed only with alkali tartrates in the ratio of 1:1. Unfortunately neither any data nor any graph in regard to the free acid are recorded.

From conductometric titration, measurements of electrical conductivity and absorption spectrum of solutions of copper nitrate and tartaric acid it has been definitely shown that the reaction occurs in the ratio of 1:1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials.—Solutions prepared from Merck's copper nitrate, chloride and tartaric acid of reagent quality were used. For determination of purity both copper and tartaric acid were estimated iodometrically.

Conductometric Measurements.—All conductometric measurements were made by Philip's universal conductivity Bridge (model GM 4140) provided with 1000 cycle audio-frequency oscillator and magic eye. In conductometric titration copper nitrate solution was treated with tartaric acid and *vice versa*. The experimental data are plotted in Figs. 1 and 2. Besides conductometric titration, conductance measurements were made both in equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions. Conductance was measured of each of the individual components as well as of their mixtures in varying proportions keeping the total volume constant. Tables I-II contain the

TABLE I
Conductivity experiment of $M/10$ -copper nitrate with $M/10$ -tartaric acid.
Temp. = 30° . (Fig. 3, curve 1).

Copper nitrate soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^4 = C_1$	Tartaric acid soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (3) $\times 10^4 = C_3$	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_5$	$M/10$ copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln. added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (6) $\times 10^4 = C_6$	$(C_1 - C_3)$
1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	264.6	0 c.c.	—	—	264.6	50 c.c.	0 c.c.	264.6	0
45	5	243.9	5	45 c.c.	16.1	260.0	45	5	281.7	21.7
40	10	217.4	10	40	24.4	241.8	40	10	270.3	28.5
35	15	195.3	15	35	30.3	225.6	35	15	259.7	34.3
33.3	16.7	186.0	16.7	33.3	32.0	218.0	33.3	16.7	253.2	35.2
32.5	17.5	181.8	17.5	32.5	32.8	214.6	32.5	17.5	250.0	35.4
30	20	170.9	20	30	35.1	206.0	30	20	242.4	36.4
27.5	22.5	158.7	22.5	27.5	37.7	196.4	27.5	22.5	233.9	37.5
25	25	146.0	25	25	40.0	186.0	25	25	224.7	38.7
22.5	27.5	133.0	27.5	22.5	41.8	174.8	22.5	27.5	211.9	37.1
20	30	119.5	30	20	43.9	163.4	20	30	198.8	35.4
17.5	32.5	106.4	32.5	17.5	45.9	152.3	17.5	32.5	185.5	33.2
16.7	33.3	101.0	33.3	16.7	46.5	147.5	16.7	33.3	180.2	32.7
15	35	93.5	35	15	47.6	141.1	15	35	172.4	31.3
10	40	64.5	40	10	51.6	115.5	10	40	140.3	24.8
5	45	33.3	45	5	54.1	87.4	5	45	103.1	15.8
—	—	—	50	0	56.2	56.2	0	50	56.2	9

experimental data of equimolecular and Tables III-V, those of non-equimolecular solutions respectively. In curves I-II (Fig. 3) and curves I-III (Fig. 4) the divergences from the additivity rule are plotted against the composition of the mixtures for equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions respectively. In all measurements the reciprocal of the observed resistance, *i.e.* conductance being sufficient to draw the graph, the cell constant was not determined.

Absorption Measurements.—Absorption measurements were made by Lunatron Fluorescence meter (model 402 E. F.) of Photovolt Corporation. In this case also the absorption of both equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions was measured. The experimental data are given in Tables VI-XI for equimolecular and in XII-XIV for non-equimolecular solutions respectively. In curves I-IV (Fig. 5) and I-II (Fig. 6) and I-III (Fig. 7) the divergences from the additivity rule are plotted against composition of the mixtures for equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions respectively. In all the cases optical density has been plotted against composition of the mixture. Absorption due to complex formation and also of copper are in the same region (red). Wave-lengths 640, 660, 700 and 730 μ have been used for equimolecular and 700 and 730 μ for non-equimolecular solutions. All the measurements have been made at room temperature varying between 30° and 32°.

TABLE II

Conductivity experiment of *M/20-copper chloride with M/20-tartaric acid.*
Temp. = 30°. (Fig. 3, curve II).

Copper chloride soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^4 = C_1$	Tartaric acid soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (3) $\times 10^4 = C_2$	$(C_1 + C_2) = C_3$	Copper chloride soln.	Tartaric acid soln. added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (6) $\times 10^4 = C_4$	$(C_4 - C_3)$
1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	125.0	—	—	—	125.0	50 c.c.	0 c.c.	125.0	0
45	5	114.9	5 c.c.	45 c.c.	8.7	123.6	45	5	129.9	6.3
40	10	103.6	10	40	14.3	117.9	40	10	129.0	11.1
35	15	92.6	15	35	17.5	110.1	35	15	124.2	14.1
33.3	16.7	88.5	16.7	33.3	18.5	107.0	33.3	16.7	122.0	15.0
32.5	17.5	86.5	17.5	32.5	19.6	105.8	32.5	17.5	121.2	15.4
30	20	80.0	20	30	20.8	100.8	30	20	117.0	16.2
27.5	22.5	74.1	22.5	27.5	22.2	96.3	27.5	22.5	113.3	17.0
25	25	67.1	25	25	23.5	90.6	25	25	108.7	18.1
22.5	27.5	61.0	27.5	22.5	24.8	85.8	22.5	27.5	103.3	17.5
20	30	54.1	30	20	26.0	80.1	20.0	30.0	97.1	17.0
17.5	32.5	48.8	32.5	17.5	26.7	75.5	17.5	32.5	91.7	16.2
16.7	33.3	46.5	33.3	16.7	27.2	73.7	16.7	33.3	89.3	15.6
15	35	42.6	35	15	27.8	70.4	15	35	85.2	14.8
10	40	29.4	40	10	30.3	59.7	10	40	70.4	10.7
5	45	15.4	45	5	32.1	47.5	5	45	53.2	5.7
0	—	—	50	0	33.3	33.3	0	50	33.3	—

TABLE III

Conductivity experiment of $M/20$ -copper nitrate with $M/5$ -tartaric acid.
Temp. = 30° . (Fig. 4, curve I)

Copper nitrate soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^4 = C_1$.	Tartaric acid soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (3) $\times 10^4 = C_3$.	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_4$.	Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln. added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (6) $\times 10^4 = C_6$.	$(C_4 - C_5)$.
1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	144.9	—	—	—	144.9	50 c.c.	0 c.c.	144.9	0
45	5	136.1	5 c.c.	45 c.c.	21.7	160.8	45	5	190.5	29.7
40	10	120.5	10	40	36.5	157.0	40	10	194.6	37.6
37.5	12.5	114.3	12.5	37.5	41.2	155.5	37.5	12.5	194.2	38.7
36	14	111.1	14	36	43.5	154.6	36	14	193.4	38.8
35.5	14.5	109.5	14.5	35.5	44.4	153.9	35.5	14.5	193.2	39.5
35	15	108.3	15	35	45.1	153.4	35	15	192.3	38.9
32.5	17.5	101.0	17.5	32.5	49.3	150.3	32.5	17.5	188.3	38.0
30	20	94.3	20	30	52.1	146.4	30	20	183.5	37.1
25	25	80.0	25	25	58.8	138.8	25	25	173.0	34.2
20	30	64.5	30	20	64.5	129.0	20	30	160.0	31.0
15	35	50.5	35	15	69.9	120.4	15	35	144.9	24.5
10	40	34.5	40	10	75.2	109.7	10	40	126.6	16.9
—	—	—	50	0	84.8	84.8	—	50	84.8	0

TABLE IV

Conductivity experiment of $M/20$ -copper nitrate with $M/10$ -tartaric acid.
Temp. = 30° . (Fig. 4, curve II).

Copper nitrate soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^4 = C_1$.	Tartaric acid soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (3) $\times 10^4 = C_3$.	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_4$.	Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln. added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (6) $\times 10^4 = C_6$.	$(C_4 - C_5)$.
1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	142.9	—	—	—	142.9	50 c.c.	0 c.c.	142.9	0
40	10	117.6	10 c.c.	40 c.c.	24.1	141.7	40	10	165.3	23.6
35	15	104.2	15	35	30.3	134.5	35	15	162.1	27.6
32.5	17.5	98.0	17.5	32.5	32.8	130.8	32.5	17.5	159.5	28.7
30.5	19.5	91.7	19.5	30.5	34.5	126.2	30.5	19.5	155.5	29.3
30	20	90.5	20	30	35.0	125.5	30	20	155.0	29.5
29.5	20.5	89.0	20.5	29.5	35.6	124.6	29.5	20.5	153.8	29.2
27.5	22.5	83.3	22.5	27.5	37.2	120.5	27.5	22.5	149.3	28.8
25	25	77.5	25	25	39.5	117.0	25	25	143.9	26.9
22.5	27.5	70.4	27.5	22.5	41.7	112.1	22.5	27.5	137.4	25.3
20	30	63.7	30	20	43.9	107.6	20	30	131.1	23.5
15	35	49.3	35	15	47.6	96.9	15	35	116.6	19.7
10	40	33.9	40	10	51.9	84.9	10	40	99.0	14.1
—	—	—	50	0	56.2	56.2	0	50	56.2	0

TABLE V

Conductivity experiment of $M/30$ -copper nitrate with $M/10$ -tartaric acid.
Temp. = 30° . (Fig. 4, curve III).

Copper nitrate soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^4 = C_1$.	Tartaric acid soln.	Water added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (3) $\times 10^4 = (C_3)$.	$(C_1 + C_3) = C_2$.	Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln. added.	Conduct. of the soln. in col. (6) $\times 10^4 = C_4$.	$(C_1 - C_3)$.
1		2	3		4	5	6		7	8
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	105.8	—	—	—	105.8	50 c.c.	0 c.c.	105.8	0
40	10	87.7	10 c.c.	40 c.c.	25.3	113.0	40	10	132.5	19.5
37.5	12.5	82.0	12.5	37.5	28.6	110.6	37.5	12.5	131.6	21.0
35	15	76.3	15	35	31.3	108.1	35	15	130.7	22.6
32.5	17.5	72.4	17.5	32.5	34.1	106.5	32.5	17.5	129.9	23.4
32	18	71.2	18	32	34.5	105.7	32	18	129.4	23.7
31.5	18.5	69.9	18.5	31.5	34.8	104.7	31.5	18.5	128.2	23.5
30	20	67.1	20	30	36.0	104.0	30	20	126.6	22.6
27.5	22.5	62.5	22.5	27.5	30.2	101.7	27.5	22.5	123.5	21.8
25	25	57.1	25	25	41.5	98.6	25	25	119.0	20.4
20	30	45.9	30	20	46.1	92.0	20	30	118.7	16.7
15	35	35.7	35	15	49.8	85.5	15	35	99.0	13.5
10	40	24.4	40	10	53.2	77.6	10	40	86.2	8.6
—	—	—	50	0	58.4	58.4	0	50	58.4	0

TABLE VI

Absorption measurement of $M/50$ -copper nitrate with $M/50$ -tartaric acid.
(Fig. 5, curve 1)

Wave-length used = $730m\mu$.

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
1		2	3	4
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	33.7	33.7	0
45	5	31.9	29.7	2.2
40	10	30.1	27.0	3.1
35	15	27.6	23.6	4.0
30	20	24.5	20.2	4.3
25	25	21.5	16.8	4.7
20	30	18.0	13.5	4.5
15	35	14.0	10.0	4.0
10	40	10.0	6.8	3.2
5	45	5.8	3.4	2.2
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE VII

Absorption measurement of M/50-copper nitrate with M/50-tartaric acid.
(Fig. 5, curve II)

Wave-length used = 700m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
1		2	3	4
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	32.8	32.8	0
45	5	31.0	29.5	1.5
40	10	28.8	26.0	2.8
35	15	27.8	23.0	3.8
30	20	23.7	19.7	4.0
25	25	20.8	16.4	4.4
20	30	17.4	13.1	4.3
15	35	13.8	9.8	3.7
10	40	9.2	6.5	2.7
5	45	5.1	3.3	1.8
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE VIII

Absorption measurement of M/50-copper nitrate with M/50-tartaric acid.
(Fig. 5, curve I1)

Wave-length used = 660m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	17.1	17.1	0
45	5	16.0	15.4	0.6
40	10	14.9	13.7	1.2
35	15	13.5	12.0	1.5
30	20	12.0	10.0	2.0
25	25	10.8	8.5	2.3
20	30	9.0	6.9	2.1
15	35	6.8	5.1	1.7
10	40	4.5	3.3	1.1
5	45	2.2	1.7	0.5
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE IX

Absorption measurement of M/50-copper nitrate with M/50-tartaric acid.

(Fig. 5, curve IV)

Wave-length used = 640m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^3 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^3 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	12.5	12.5	0
45	5	11.9	11.5	0.4
40	10	11.2	10.2	1.0
35	15	10.2	8.8	1.4
30	20	9.3	7.5	1.8
25	25	8.3	6.2	2.1
20	30	6.8	5.0	1.8
15	35	5.1	3.8	1.3
10	40	3.2	2.5	0.7
5	45	1.4	1.2	0.2
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE X

Absorption measurement of M/30-copper nitrate with M/30-tartaric acid.

(Fig. 6, curve I)

Wave-length used = 700m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^3 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^3 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	53.7	53.7	0
40	10	48.2	43.2	5.0
35	15	44.4	38.0	6.4
30	20	41.0	32.6	8.4
27.5	22.5	39.0	29.8	9.2
25	25	36.7	27.0	9.7
22.5	27.5	33.0	24.0	9.0
20	30	29.7	21.6	8.1
15	35	22.6	16.2	6.4
10	40	16.1	10.8	5.3
5	50	—	—	0

TABLE XI

Absorption measurement $M/40$ -copper nitrate with $M/40$ -tartaric acid.

(Fig. 6, curve II)

Wave-length used = $730m\mu$.

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	41.5	42.5	0
40	10	38.2	34.0	4.2
35	15	35.2	29.8	5.4
30	20	31.9	25.5	6.4
27.5	22.5	30.1	23.5	6.6
25	25	28.4	21.3	7.1
22.5	27.5	26.0	19.2	6.8
20	30	23.2	17.0	6.2
15	35	18.4	12.8	5.6
10	40	13.0	8.5	4.5
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE XII

Absorption measurement of $M/50$ -copper nitrate with $M/10$ -tartaric acid.

(Fig. 7, curve I)

Wave-length used = $730m\mu$.

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	33.7	33.7	0
40	10	34.2	26.8	7.4
37.5	12.5	33.3	25.1	8.2
35	15	32.3	23.5	8.8
33.5	16.5	31.9	22.6	9.3
32.5	17.5	30.8	21.8	9.0
30	20	28.8	20.1	8.7
25	25	25.2	16.8	8.4
20	30	21.5	13.5	8.0
10	40	12.8	6.8	6.0
0	50	—	—	0

TABLE XIII

Absorption measurement of M/50-copper nitrate with M/10-tartaric acid.

(Fig. 7, curve II)

Wave-length used = 700m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	32.8	32.8	0
40	10	33.3	26.0	7.3
37.5	12.5	32.3	24.5	7.8
35	15	31.5	22.8	8.7
33.5	16.5	31.0	21.8	9.2
32.5	17.5	29.9	21.1	8.8
30	20	28.0	19.5	8.5
25	25	24.4	16.3	8.1
20	30	20.4	13.0	7.4
10	40	12.0	6.6	5.4
0	50	—	—	—

TABLE XIV

Absorption measurement of M/40-copper nitrate with M/10-tartaric acid.

(Fig. 7, curve III)

Wave-length used = 730m μ .

Copper nitrate soln.	Tartaric acid soln.	Optical density of the soln. in col. (1) $\times 10^2 = (D_1)$.	(Exptl.) optical density in case of no reaction $\times 10^2 = (D_2)$.	$(D_1 - D_2) = D$.
(1)		(2)	(3)	(4)
50 c.c.	0 c.c.	42.5	42.5	0
40	10	42.0	33.7	8.3
35	15	40.0	29.5	10.5
32.5	17.5	38.7	27.5	11.2
30	20	36.2	25.5	10.7
27.5	22.5	33.7	23.5	10.2
25	25	31.0	21.3	9.7
20	30	26.0	17.0	9.0
10	40	14.3	8.0	6.3
0	50	—	—	0

DISCUSSION

It will be seen that the conductometric titration curves (Fig. 1 and 2) are almost continuous, although a slight break can be noticed when the ratio of the reactants is 1:1. It cannot therefore be definitely concluded that the reaction occurs in that

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Curves I and II represent respectively
 I— $M/10\text{-Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10\text{-tartaric acid}$ and
 II— $M/20\text{-CuCl}_2 + M/20\text{-tartaric acid}$.

FIG. 4

I— $M/20\text{-Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/5\text{-tartaric acid}$
 II— " " + $M/10$ " "
 III— $M/30$ " + " "

FIG. 5

I-IV refer to $M/50$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/50$ -tartaric acid in 730, 700, 660 and 640 μ respectively.

FIG. 6

Curves I and II represent respectively $M/30$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/30$ -tartaric acid in 700 μ and $M/40$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/40$ -tartaric acid in 730 μ .

FIG. 7

I-II represent $M/50$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10$ -tartaric acid respectively to 730, 700 μ and III represents $M/40$ - $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 + M/10$ -tartaric acid in 730 μ .

proportion. The continuous nature of the curves may be due to the fact that the complex is less stable in acid medium and the statement of Bobtelsky and Jordan (*loc. cit.*) that the free acid forms no complex is perhaps due to the same cause.

The conductance measurements leads definitely to the conclusion that the reaction occurs when the ratio of the reactants is 1:1. It will be observed that in equimolecular solutions a maximum is obtained at that ratio, when the divergence from the additivity rule due to complex formation is plotted against composition (Fig. 3, curves I-II). The experimental data show that the observed conductance of the mixture is greater than the sum of the conductance of the individual components. The increase in conductance can only be attributed to the liberation of highly mobile hydrogen ion from tartaric acid molecule as a result of

reaction between the salt and the acid.

Measurement of absorption of equimolecular solution in different wave-lengths also supports the conclusion of the conductance measurements (Fig. 5, curve I-IV; Fig. 6, curves I-II).

The experimental results leave no doubt that in dilute solutions only one complex is formed between cupric ion and free tartaric acid in the ratio of 1:1. The reaction occurs probably as follows :

Now by applying Job's method of continued variation the instability constant can be calculated from the measurements of conductance and absorption in non-equimolecular solutions.

The equation relating to the value of K , the instability constant, is given by,

$$K = \frac{C\{(p+1)x-1\}^2}{(p-1)(1-2x)},$$

where C is the molar concentration of copper nitrate, M , the molar concentration of tartaric acid, x , c.c. of tartaric acid combining with $(1-x)$ c.c. of copper nitrate to give the maximum effect.

TABLE XV

Conductometric measurement.

Table No	Fig. No.	Curve No.	C .	p .	$\frac{p}{C}$	x .	$K \times 10^3$.	Mean $K \times 10^3$.
V	4	I	0.05	4		0.29	0.80	
VI	4	II	0.05	2		0.40	1.05	0.96
VII	4	III	0.033	3		0.36	1.00	

TABLE XVI

Absorption measurement.

Table No.	Fig. No.	Curve No.	Wave-length.	C .	p .	x .	$K \times 10^3$.	Mean $K \times 10^3$.
XII	7	I	730m μ	0.02	5	0.33	1.43	
XIII	7	II	700	0.02	5	0.33	1.43	1.47
XIV	7	III	730	0.025	4	0.35	1.57	

The mean value of K obtained from the two methods is 1.21×10^{-2} .

Further work with alkali tartrate is in progress.

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